

STORY MAP TECHNIQUES IN DEVELOPING COMPREHENSIVE SKILLS AMONG SCHOOL CHILDREN: A QUASI-EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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Abstract

The story map approach is acknowledged as a useful tool for differentiating between important and irrelevant information in the narrative & guiding students, **Aims** : To evaluate the effectiveness of story map technique and level of comprehensive skills among school children in experimental. **Methodology**. The researchers used a quasi-experimental design with purposive sampling to study the effectiveness of story map technique on the level of comprehensive skills among children in selected school at Chennai. They gathered data using structured questionnaires and maintained confidentiality throughout the study. They analyzed the data using descriptive and inferential statistics. **Result**: The calculated t value 1.33 reveals that there was a significant difference between the post test mean value of experimental and control group. This indicates the difference between the post test means in both the experimental and control group is a true difference. The results of the study showed that was significantly effective in improving the level of comprehensive skills in children.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Story Map Technique, Comprehensive Skill, School Children.

INTRODUCTION

“Children are the future of country and are the special gift to the world. If the child is having good health without proper education, the child will not have a good future”. [1] Once upon a time a phrase that attracts children and adults to motivate the children to listen to the class. [2] Telling a story is not useful for the children to understand the meaning of the story. [3] If a person’s goes to a new place he needs a map to guide him to reach the correct destination. [4] Likewise if a teacher wants to tell a story to the children she needs a guide which makes the children to understand the setting, major characters, problem in the story, events, and the moral of the story. [5] A study focused specifically on retelling as a post reading strategy. [6] Retelling is a skill that calls on students to tell the story again in their own words in the correct order. [7] In order to do this, students must remember the story, pick out the important pieces, and tell the story once again in the correct order. [8] A retelling is different than a summary in that a summary reduces story length and only reports main ideas or topics, while a retelling recount all story events, details, and even story language and phrases. [9 - 10] Retelling is a skill that helps students organize, summarize, and process information that they have read or heard. [11]

The story map technique is accepted as an effective technique in distinguishing significant and insignificant information in this story, directing student (making them focus on important components), providing active participation, and transferring information in to long-term memory activating for knowledge and predicting. By mapping the story, the student will record their thoughts and represent it to the

organizer. It will help the student to comprehend to the story because the students will focus on what they read. [12]

The story mapping helps students perceive the sequence of story development. In story mapping is particularly useful to help the students to develop a sense of story and realize that the setting, events, and character of a story are interrelated. In other words, a story map leads the students to form a mental picture of story's structure and to understand the related story part in narrative text.[13] The purpose of the study is to assess the pretest level of comprehensive skills among school children in experimental and control group & to evaluate the effectiveness of story map technique and level of comprehensive skills among school children in experimental group & to find out the association between level of comprehensive skills among school children with their selected demographic variables.

MATERIALS & METHODS

A quasi-experimental research design was used to study the effectiveness of story map technique on the level of comprehensive skills among children in a SRM School, Chennai. Sixty children were selected using purposive sampling. Children who are absent on the day of data collection and children who are sick and those who were unwilling to participate in the study were excluded. The parents of the participants were informed about the study and their consent was obtained. The project was approved by the ethics committee of the institution. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire. Confidentiality was maintained throughout the study. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results show in experimental group majority of 16(53.3%) children were in the age group of 5-7 years, 18(60%) females than the males, 11(36.7%) hindus than the other regions, 13(43.3%) most them completed undergraduate, 16(53.3%) living in nuclear family and 14(46.7%) employed in private sector. In control Group majority of 18(60%) children were in the age group of 5-7 years, 15(50%) females & males equally, 12(40%) hindus than the other regions, 16(53.3%) most them completed undergraduate, 13(43.3%) living in nuclear family and 17(56.6%) employed in private sector.

Table 1: Assessment of pre-test and post-test score level of comprehensive skills among control and experimental group

N = 60

Level of The Comprehensive Skills	Experimental Group				Control Group			
	Pre Test		Post Test		Pre Test		Post Test	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Inadequate	20	66.7	3	10	15	50	14	46.7
Moderate	5	16.7	10	33.3	9	30	11	36.7
Adequate	5	16.7	17	56.7	6	20	5	16.7

Table 1 shows that in experimental group 20(66.7%) of them had inadequate level of Comprehensive skills in pretest. whereas in post – test majority of the school children's 17(56.7 %) of them had adequate level of Comprehensive skills. In control group in pretest majority of the children's 15(50%) of them had inadequate level of

Comprehensive skills, whereas in posttest majority of the school children's 11(36.7%) of them had moderate level of Comprehensive skills.

Table 2: Effectiveness of level of comprehensive skills in control and experimental group

N = 60

Group	Pretest		Post Test		Mean Difference score	Paired 't' test & p-value
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D		
Experimental group	3.8	2.87	7.52	2.29	3.72	t = -5.6029 p=0.0001, S***
Control group	3.47	2.43	8.63	1.88	5.16	t = -9.19923 p=0.0001, S***

***p<0.001, S – Significant

The data shows that comparison of pre test and post test values of Experimental group. The calculated t value 3.72(12.4%) is greater than the table value, there was a significant difference exists in the mean of pre test and post test, in can be calculated there was an improvement in the comprehensive skills. Whereas comparison of pre test and post test values of Control group. The calculated t value 5.16(17.2%) is greater than the table value, there was a significant difference exists in the mean of pre test and post test, in can be calculated there was an improvement in the comprehensive skills.

The data shows the association of demographic variables with the post test scores of levels of comprehensive skills. There is no association exists among the selected demographic variables.

DISCUSSION

This study is supported by Sholichah, N. I. (2017) the results showed that there was a significant difference between the scores of students before teaching reading comprehension skills to them using story map and after using story map. With regard to this finding, it can be inferred that the reading comprehension skills of the experimental group were significantly different after 16 instructional sessions. [14] Another supported this finding is Isikdogan, Necla & Kargin, Tevhide. (2010).

Who conducted study on Investigation of the Effectiveness of the Story-Map Method on Reading Comprehension Skills among Students with Mental Retardation. The finds states that a pre-test post-test experimental design with a control group was used. The findings showed that the story mapping method positively affected the reading comprehension skills of the students in the experimental group. [15]

CONCLUSION

The story map technique was found effective method to improve the level of Comprehensive skills among school children. The findings of this study provided evidence that the use of story map and story map questions was effective in improving the narrative story among school children.

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Authors Contribution

All the authors actively participated in the work of study. All the authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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